

Synthesis, growth and characterizations of organic nonlinear optical material : 4-Chloroaniline

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Abstract : The organic nonlinear optical crystal 4-chloroaniline was grown from methanol at room temperature by low temperature solution growth method. Powder X-ray diffraction was studied to confirm the grown crystal structure. The cutoff wavelength for the grown crystal was observed at 325 nm and the band gap energy of 3.814 eV was determined by recording the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum analysis. The presence of different functional groups of 4-chloroaniline were identified by FT-IR spectral analysis. The position of proton was found out by using ^1H FT-NMR spectral analysis. The thermal stability of the crystal was carried out by TG-DTG analysis. The SHG efficiency for 4-chloroaniline was measured by Kurtz-Perry powder technique and the grown crystal is suitable for NLO application.

Keywords : Solution growth, energy band gap, FT-NMR, SHG.

Introduction

In our scientific and modern world, the study of organic nonlinear optical (NLO) materials has attracted more attention due to their applications like frequency conversion, optical signal processing, electro-optic modulation, optical switching and logic gates. Organic crystals are especially interesting because they offer highly aligned stable orientation of NLO chromophores in the crystal lattice¹⁻⁵. 4-Chloroaniline ($\text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$) is an organochlorine compound. It is employed as an intermediate in the industrial synthesis in the range of pesticides, pigments and azo-dyes, as well as for the production of pharmaceuticals and cosmetic products⁶. Harlan C. Meal has analyzed the Zeeman quadrupole spectra in the 4-chloroaniline crystal. There are two sets of chlorine atoms in the 4-chloroaniline crystal with differently oriented electrical field gradients⁷. Sharma *et al.* has reported that the binary phase diagram of 4-chloroaniline and 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde⁸. To the best of our knowledge there is no report available in the growth part of 4-chloroaniline single crystal. Hence in this paper, we have reported the growth and characterization of 4-chloroaniline single crystal.

Results and discussion

Powder X-ray diffraction studies :

The powder XRD patterns were collected by BRUKER

D8 ADVANCED powder X-ray diffractometer with the wavelength of $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. The 4-chloroaniline single crystals were crushed into fine powder form and scanned over a range of $10-60^\circ$ at a rate of $2^\circ/\text{min}$. POWDER X software package was used to index the intense peak. Fig. 1 represents the X-ray diffraction pattern of 4-chloroaniline crystal. The calculated cell parameters are $a = 7.38 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.64 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.24 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$. The crystal belongs to orthorhombic system with space group of $\text{Pn}2_1\text{a}$ which has a volume of $V = 590 \text{ \AA}^3$. The obtained unit cell parameters and space group are in good agreement with the reported results⁹.

Fig. 1. Powder XRD pattern of 4-chloroaniline.

UV-Vis-NIR spectral studies :

The transmission spectrum of the crystal was recorded with the help of Perkin-Elmer Model – Lambda 35 Spectrometer having the spectral region of 200–1100 nm. From this analysis, the grown crystal of thickness 3 mm was used and the crystal had a cut-off wavelength of 325 nm which shows that it could be applicable for NLO application throughout the entire visible and IR region. The optical absorption coefficient (α) was estimated by using the following relation,

$$\alpha = \frac{2.3026 \log (1/T)}{d} \quad (1)$$

where T is the transmittance and d is the thickness of the crystal.

The optical band gap energy was calculated from the transmission spectrum,

$$E = \frac{A\sqrt{(h\nu - E_g)}}{h\nu} \quad (2)$$

where A is constant, E_g is the optical band gap of the crystal, h is the Planck's constant, ν is the frequency of the incident photons. The plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy (eV) is as shown in Fig. 2. From this above observation E_g was evaluated by the extrapolation of the linear part of the graph¹⁰. The optical energy band gap was found to be 3.814 eV.

Fig. 2. Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs photon energy of 4-chloroaniline.

FT-IR studies :

FT-IR spectrum of 4-chloroaniline crystal was observed between the regions of 4000 to 500 cm^{-1} by Shimadzu

Model IR Affinity-1 Spectrometer. The potassium bromide pellet technique was used in the spectrometer to study the functional groups presented in the grown crystal. The band obtained at 3471 cm^{-1} is due to the NH_2 symmetric stretching modes. Two sharp bands of medium intensity located at 1087 and 1004 cm^{-1} are due to the in-plane deformation of the aromatic C-H stretching modes. Para substituted benzene shows C-Cl bond stretching vibration in the region 800–840 cm^{-1} and in this spectrum the stretching vibration C-Cl appears at $\sim 819 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹¹.

FT-NMR analysis :

The grown crystal was powdered and dissolved in deuterated chloroform for recording NMR analysis by Bruker AC 400-NMR Spectrometer. The ^1H FT-NMR signals found for the sample are illustrated in Fig. 3. The peak at 7.25 to 6.59 ppm corresponds to aromatic protons. The peak at 3.47 ppm corresponds to the NH_2 protons. There are two doublet peaks at 7.10–7.08 ppm and 6.61–6.59 ppm and a singlet at 3.47 ppm.

Fig. 3. ^1H FT-NMR spectrum of 4-chloroaniline.

Thermal analysis :

The thermal behavior of 4-chloroaniline was carried out in temperature ranging from 30–580 $^\circ\text{C}$ in the inert NO_2 atmosphere at a heating rate of 20 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ by TGA Q500 V20.10 BUILD 36. From the TGA, we observe that, the peak occurred at 92 $^\circ\text{C}$ was due to the melting point of the substance. The DTG plot shows that the substance decomposition at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ causing the major weight loss of the sample.

Nonlinear optical study :

The nonlinear optical property of crystal was examined by the Kurtz and Perry powder technique¹². In the present study, the grown crystal was crushed well and tightly packed between two transparent glass slides (sample cell). A Q-switched Nd : YAG laser operated at the fundamental wavelength of 1064 nm using the pulse energy of 0.68 Joule was passed through the sample cell. The photomultiplier and digitalizing oscilloscope were used to measure the amplitude of the SHG output signal was found to be 8.8 mJ. The emission of the green light from the sample confirmed the second harmonic generation. The SHG efficiency of the grown crystal was comparable to that of KDP.

Experimental

Synthesis and crystal growth :

Commercially available 4-chloroaniline was used as the starting material. It was taken along with methanol as a solvent in the equimolar ratio, which was stirred well for two hours to attain the homogenized solution and filtered using a Whatman filter paper. The pH value of the solution was 6.57. The saturated solution was transferred to a petridish, wrapped with a punctured polythene cover, away from dust. After 10 days the grown crystals were harvested with the dimension of $7 \times 5 \times 3$ mm³.

Conclusion

4-Chloroaniline single crystal was grown by solution growth method. The grown crystal belongs to orthorhombic system and the unit cell parameters were assessed using powder XRD method. The UV-Vis-NIR spectral analysis was carried out and the crystal had a cut-off wavelength of 325 nm. The optical energy band gap was calculated as 3.814 eV. The functional groups had been identified from the FT-IR analysis. The FT-NMR spectrum confirmed the molecular structure of the compound. The TG-DTG results revealed that the stability of the sample was up to 150 °C. The nonlinear property was

evaluated by Q-switched Nd : YAG laser and the second harmonic generation efficiency of 4-chloroaniline single crystals are comparable to that of KDP.

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